

A Study on Factors Affecting Consumer's Buying Behavior towards Home Loan with Special Reference to State Bank of India and Life Insurance Corporation, in Bargar Taluk

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Abstract

Everybody wants to own a home. The person gets shelter in the home to take rest and feel comfortable. Many commercial banks and financial institutions give a loan for the home to the people who want to own a home. To attract consumers, banks provide home loans at the cheaper rate. Currently, banks offer the cheapest loan for homes, as a gesture of a customer-friendly attitude. The present study was undertaken with the intent to investigate after examining the literature reviewed and noticed that their exit gap regarding consumer factors affecting perception towards the home loan disbursed by banks. Accordingly, the problem of the study focuses on customer views towards the housing loan schemes of the bank. An attempt has also been made for the study of banks delivery and disbursement of loan leading to consumer buying behavior.

Keywords: Home Finance, factors of SBI and LIC.

Introduction

The housing finance sector in India has experienced the unprecedented change in its structure since its formulation stage of being a solely a government undertaking to a very competitive sector with a large number of financing entities all over India. The paper aims to study the various factors that influence the decision of the consumer for taking Home Loan. The paper focuses on the Home loan offered by LIC and SBI and makes a comparative analysis of the factors that affect the consumers. The paper has a practical implication both for the academicians and for the readers regarding their concern with the aspect issues regarding factors influencing the buyer behavior towards Home loans. The paper is original and the highlights of the paper can be used for further research purpose and provide the knowledge base to the readers.

The concept of housing finance and the housing finance systems have been evolving. According to LoicChiquier and Michael Lea, "Housing finance brings together complex and multi-sector issues that are driven by constantly changing local features, such as a country's legal environment or culture, economic makeup, regulatory environment, or political system." The demand for housing has increased day by day. Housing finance plays an important role as an engine of equitable economic growth though the reduction of poverty and prevents slum proliferation in the economy. To meet the growing housing demand the government needs to provide the finance for housing to the people. The housing finance sector in India has experienced the unprecedented change in its structure since its formulation stage of being a solely a government undertaking to a very competitive sector with a large number of financing entities all over India. Home is a place where we relax after coming back from our day's tiring work; it is the place where we can give time to our family and spend beautiful moments with them. After years of thinking, anticipating, saving and research, we finally decide to build our dream house. At the time, finance is the major criteria which pull back everyone from moving towards the cherished goal.

To acquire a home which can be christened as our 'Own House' is a life-time decision and has to be made with efficient planning and requires huge finance. Our Dream Home is not far away with a Home Loan which will fulfill our dream into a reality. Home Loan is a Secured Loan offered by a bank against the security of a house/property which could be a personal property or a commercial one. It is a loan collected by a borrower from a bank issued against the property/security intended to be bought on the part by the borrower giving the banker a conditional ownership over the property, i.e., If the borrower has failed to pay back the loan, the banker can retrieve the finance by selling the property.

History of Home Loan

Own a home. There will probably be changes, especially in such areas as interest rates, simply because the housing market changes at different times, depending on the national economy. Real estate is currently one of the fastest growing sectors in India. The banking sector is also registering the profitable business for the last few decades, with the growth of real estate. Majority of the banks are also offering easy home loans at attractive rates to their customers. Now that getting a home loan is so easy, it seems everyone can fulfill his / her long-cherished dreams of purchasing lands, building their houses and expanding their homes. A home loan, or mortgage, is a secured loan that borrowers obtain to purchase a home. As a home is the largest purchase many individuals will ever make, most borrowers prefer home loans. Most loans paid for promptly result For many years, the only way to obtain money to purchase a home was to apply for a conventional home loan. This type of loan was obtained through a bank, credit union or other private, non-government-affiliated financial institution. In 1938, the Federal National Mortgage Association, better known as "Fannie Mae," was created and established as a federal agency by the President Mr. Franklin Roosevelt as a part of his New Deal. This made it possible, even during those days, when most people had little income were still be able to afford a home. In 1970, the Federal Home Loan Mortgage Corporation, known as "Freddie Mac," was created to lessen the "monopolization" of home lending that Fannie Mae enjoyed. Both Fannie Mae and Freddie Mac, once considered as "government" auspices, are private establishments now. World War II came along, and hundreds of citizens went to war. When it ended, they returned home to pick up their lives where they had left off, or to start a new life. These people needed places to live, so the Serviceman's Readjustment Act of 1944, Public Law 78-346, was enacted. This made it possible for veterans to borrow money for the purchase or building of a house. Several major changes in the Act have been made in the years since 1944, allowing veterans of subsequent wars, such as Korea, Vietnam and, most recently, the Gulf wars, to have

the same advantages in obtaining home loans. All home loans---conventional, VA, Fannie Mae, and Freddie Mac--accomplished the same goal: they allowed people to become homeowners. The Veteran's Administration, Fannie Mae and Freddie Mac, however, provided a level of protection for the loans and those involved with them that other financial institutions might not necessarily have. Having different types of home loans to choose from allow more people to be able to own their own home. Depending on the terms and conditions, it may be easier to obtain a loan from one entity than from another. As long as there are financial institutions that will make home loans, there will be the opportunity for people to in a positive notation on credit reports, meaning that borrowers may be able to qualify for larger loans at better interest rates after having successfully made loan payments. Different types of home loans are tailored to suit the heterogeneous requirements of the customers. The description of some of the most common types of home loans is given below.

Types of Home Loans

Home Purchase Loans: This is the basic home loan for the purchase of a new home.

Home Improvement Loans: These loans are given for implementing repair works and renovations in a home that has already been purchased.

Home Construction Loan: This loan is available for the construction of a new home.

Home Extension Loan: This is given for expanding or extending an existing home. For instance, a customer may apply for a loan for the addition of an extra room in his/her home and similar cases.

Home Conversion Loan: This is available for those who have financed the present home with a home loan and wish to purchase and move to another home for which some extra funds are required. Through home conversion loan, the existing loan is transferred to the new home including the extra amount required, eliminating the need for pre-payment of the previous loan.

Land Purchase Loans: This loan is available for the purchase of land for both construction and investment purpose.

Bridge Loans: Bridge Loans are designed for people who wish to sell the existing home and purchase another one. The bridge loans help finance the new home.

Balance Transfer Loans: Balance transfer loans help to pay off an existing home loan and avail the option of a loan with a lower rate of interest.

Features of Home Loan

Home loans are available on the fixed rate of interest as well as floating rate of interest. In fixed rate loans, the interest rate remains fixed over the life of the loan, irrespective of the interest rates in the open market. The plus point of fixed-rate loans is that they remain steady over the years. However, the flip side is that the lenders charge a higher rate of interest for fixed-rate loans because if interest rates shoot up, they lose the opportunity to make more money on the funds they are lending. In floating rate loans, the rate of interest changes according to a set formula as interest rates fluctuate in the open market. The plus point is that lenders charge a lower rate for such loans because the borrower takes the interest-rate risk. The downside is that interest rates may rise anytime and one can end up paying more than fixed-rate loans. Hence the type of interest one opts for will entirely depend on one's personal preferences.

General Information about Home Loan

The loan amount is based on the repayment capacity of the customer. However, it cannot be more than 85% of the cost of the property (including the cost of the land).

The minimum term of the home loan is five years, while the maximum duration for the loan is 20 years, subject to the retirement age of the applicant. Home Loans can be applied either individually or jointly, with a spouse, children (son or daughter) and even earning parents (father or mother), but if staying with the applicant and having the regular income.

Home loan eligibility can be enhanced by repaying the outstanding loans, clubbing the income, increasing the home loan tenure and opting for a step-up loan. The amount of loan sanctioned varies from bank to bank. Generally, the maximum loan amount granted to the applicant would be 80% to 85% of the cost of the home.

Review of Literature

Gudadhe (2013) discussed the customer perception towards products and services of State Bank of India. The author has focussed on research by taking into account the branches of Mahatma district. The article discussed the SBI Bank Group-wise perception and satisfaction level of customers, the availability and use of products and services given by the bank. The author concluded by stating that the customer expects higher quality services from banks which, if fulfilled, could result in significantly improved customer satisfaction levels. 99.27% customers expressed their satisfaction towards the services.

Rao T. S. (2013) discussed the perception and problems of home loan takers in Andhra Pradesh. The author has focused on research by taking into account the HDFC and SBI bank. The paper discussed the Housing Policy frame work, trends and progress in Housing Finance, the operational performance of HDFC and SBI about providing housing finance to individuals, perception and problems of home loan takers in the State of Andhra Pradesh. The author concluded by stating that the Housing Finance in India faced some set-back in decades but the designing of shelter policy, the organization of the housing finance market, the introduction of fiscal incentives have brought about some changes in the housing finance. The services and product innovations are the key tools for success.

Mittal (2014) discussed the demographic profile of the customers and their choice of a particular type of bank. The author has focused on research by taking into account the customers of SBI and ICICI bank. The paper discussed the customer needs, preferences and usage rate, understand the service quality perception of customers towards retail banking services. The author concluded by stating that age, occupation and education significantly influence the customer's choice for a particular type of bank. There was a significant difference between the age-wise, education-wise and occupation-wise distribution of the two types of banks. The income of the customers and their choice of a particular type of bank were independent of each other.

Kumaraswami M. and Nayan J. (2014) discussed the importance of housing finance and the institutions providing housing finance. A detailed discussion of the marketing strategies adopted by financing institutions has been discussed by taking into account the loan criteria eligibility, loan amount, interest rate, security, loan tenure, margin and processing fee. Finally, the paper highlights the performance of the housing sector, major findings and suggestions to improve the effective marketing of housing finance for both public and private sector banks.

Gupta J. and Jain S. (2012) focused on the various practices adopted by cooperative banks in India and made a comparison of the cooperative banks concerning their efficiency concerning lending practices. The major findings of the study showed that majority (32% as per the study) of the respondent was having housing loan for the bank under study, most (64% as per the study) of the people prefer to take long-term loan which is more than 3 years, there is a very simple procedure followed by bank for loan, easy repayment and fewer formalities are the main factors determining customer's selection of loans, quality of services provided by the staff is satisfactory because

bank is catering to a small segment only and the customers are properly dealt with, customers are satisfied with the mode of repayment of installments, average time for the processing of loan is less i.e. approx 7 days. The authors also suggested measures to improve the efficiency of the Cooperative banks.

Ghosh S.(2012) in his study mainly focused on the guidelines followed by commercial banks in India regarding the appraisal process of housing loans with specific reference to Indian Overseas Bank.

Hingorani P. and Tiwari P. in the paper evaluated the present issues and challenges in the Indian urban housing market and gave suggestions for tools and approaches that can guide movement towards a more holistic approach.

Mishra A.K.(2011) discussed the overall resources invested by housing finance company in India since their incorporation and identified the area where efficiency can be improved and cost reduction is possible for optimum and effective utilization of resources.

Sridharan S. (2014) in the paper analyzed the Indian demographics and how, correspondingly, the housing finance sector has evolved. According to the author “Although there are various Government of India initiatives as well as schemes of institutions like World Bank and its members like the International Finance Corporation (IFC), there still exists a challenge at the ground level: the simple availability or production of affordable housing projects.”

The Objective of the Study

To study the various factors affecting the consumer’s decision towards the purchase of home loan of SBI and LIC.

Research Methodology

Type of Study: The study is Descriptive.

Area Of Study: Bargur Taluk

Sample Size: N = 100 respondents

Sampling Process: Random sampling technique was used for the study.

Data Type: For the study both primary as well secondary data was used.

Data Collection Tools: For the collection of primary data structured Questionnaire was used consisting of both open and closed-ended questions. Secondary data was obtained from research journals, books, and websites and published records.

Statistical Tools Used: Frequency percentage, the t-test was applied for data analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Demographic Profile of Respondents

It was found in the research that out of the total respondents, 84% were Male and 16% were female respondents. Regarding the age category, it was found in the research that 33% of the respondents were in the age group of 18-30 years, 40% of the respondents were in the age group of 31-40 years, 18% were in the age group of 41- 50 years, 08% were in the age group of 51-60 years and 01% were in the age group of 61-70 years. Out of the total respondents, 76% were married and 24% were unmarried.

Type of Home Loan Taken by Respondents

Table 1 Type of Home Loan Opted

S.No	Category of Home Loan	LIC(%)	SBI(%)
1	Home Purchase	42	48
2	Home Improvement	16	22
3	Home Construction	22	22
4	Home Extension	02	----
5	Land Purchases	18	08

As shown in Table No:1, it was found in the research that out of the total respondents of LIC, 42% of the respondents had opted for “Home Purchase”, 16% of the respondents had opted for “Home Improvement”, 22% had opted for „Home construction, 02% had opted for “Home extension”and 18% had opted for „Land Purchase - category regarding the Home loan. In case of the total respondents of SBI, it was found in the research that regarding the Home loan category, 48% of the respondents have opted for Home purchase” option, 22% of the respondents had opted for Home Improvement”, 22% of the respondents had opted for Home construction and 8% had opted for Land purchase.

Interest Rate Opted by the Respondents

Table 2 Interest Rate Opted by the Respondents

S.No	Category	LIC(%)	SBI(%)
1	Fixed Interest Rate	98	100
2	Floating Interest Rate	02	-----

As shown in Table No: 2, out of the total respondents of LIC, it was found in the research that 98% of the respondent had opted for “Fixed interest rate” and 02 % had opted for “Floating interest rate.” In the case of the total respondents of SBI, it was found in the research that 100% of the respondents had opted for” Fixed interest rate.”

Reason for Selecting SBI or LIC for Taking the Home Loan

The t-test was conducted to compare the reasons for selecting SBI or LIC by respondents to take the home loan.

Table 3 Reason for selecting SBI or LIC

Reason	Mean LIC	Mean SBI	t-value LIC	T-Value SBI
Low-Interest Rate	4.0000	4.1300	52.915 ***	56.563***
Accessibility in Easy	4.2600	4.3200	32.684***	32.654***
Status/Reputation of the Institution	4.3000	4.4400	55.894***	54.401***
Quick Service by the Company	4.3200	4.1200	55.433***	49.058***
Scheme Offered by the Company	4.1600	4.2400	57.734***	53.973***

P< .05=* P<.01=** P<.001=***

As shown in Table No:3, it was found in the research that the mean value for SBI (4.18) was higher as compared to the mean value of LIC (4.00) regarding the,, low-interest rate. The mean value for SBI (4.32) was higher as compared to the mean value of LIC (4.26) regarding the „Easy

Accessibility factor. The mean value for SBI (4.44) was higher as compared to the mean value of LIC (4.3) regarding the „Status/Reputation of the institution factor. The mean value for LIC (4.32) was higher as compared to the mean value of SBI (4.12) regarding the „Quick service by the company factor. The mean value for SBI (4.24) was higher as compared to the mean value of LIC (4.16) regarding the „Schemes offered factor. Thus there was a significant difference found between the variables regarding the respondent’s reason for selecting SBI or LIC as an option for taking the home loan.

Factors Influencing the Decision to Take Home Loan

The t-test was conducted to compare the factors that influenced the respondents to take home loan from SBI and LIC

Table 4 Factors that Influenced the Respondents to Take Home Loan from SBI and LIC

Factors Influencing the Decisions	Mean LIC	Mean SBI	T-Value LIC	T-Value SBI
Longer repayment period	2.4000	2.2600	22.450***	28.304***
Easy Documentation formalities	1.9000	1.9800	14.778***	15.697***
Fast processing of loan	2.3400	2.1600	18.495***	18.145***
Good communication	2.3000	2.1200	16.020***	17.667***
Co-operative staff	2.2800	2.3000	16.998***	16.020***
Easy installments	1.7400	1.8000	18.523***	19.922***
Suggestion by Friends/Relatives	1.8200	1.7400	17.216***	13.040***
Trust of Institution	1.6400	1.5800	15.474***	16.606***

P< .05=* P<.01=** P<.001=***

As shown in Table no:4, it was found in the research that regarding the „Longer repayment period” and “ Easy documentation” factor, the mean value of SBI (2.26, 1.98) was found to be higher than LIC (2.40, 1.90) respectively. Regarding “Fast processing of loan” and “Good Communication” factor, the mean value for LIC (2,34, 2.30) was found to be higher than the mean value of SBI (2.16, 2.12) respectively. Regarding the factor of “Cooperative staff and „Easy installments,” the mean value for SBI (2.30, 1.80) was found to be higher than the mean values of LIC (2.28, 1.74) respectively. Regarding “Suggestion by friends/relatives” and „trust on institution” factor, the mean value for LIC (1.82, 1.64) was found to be higher than the mean values of SBI (1.74, 1.58). Thus, there was a significant difference found between the variables regarding the factors that influence the respondents to opt for the home loan from SBI or LIC.

Major Findings

- Maximum percentage of the respondents had opted for “Home Purchase” category of Home loan, both in LIC (42%) and SBI (48%)
- “Fixed rate of interest” is the most preferred option by the respondents regarding the purchase of Home Loan.
- “Low Rate of Interest” “Easy Accessibility”, “Status/Reputation of the institution” and “Scheme offered by the company”, were the major factors that the respondents consider as the reason for selecting SBI as an institution for taking Home Loan, whereas the factor of Prompt service was found to be a major factor that the respondents consider as the reason for selecting LIC as an institution for taking Home Loan.
- “Longer repayment period”, “Easy documentation formalities”, “Cooperative staff and “Easy instalments” are the major factors that had influenced the respondents to opt for Home Loan

from SBI, whereas the factors namely “Fast processing of Loan”, “Good communication”, “Suggestion by friends/relatives” and “Trust on institution” acted as the major influencing factors that influenced the respondents to opt for Home loan from LIC.

Conclusion

The demand for Home loans has been increasing in India due to the requirements of residential accommodation. A large amount of Indian population is availing the home loan facility which is offered by the public as well as the private sector banks. It is important for the institutions offering the home loans to consider and keep track of the factors affecting the decision of the buyers to avail the home loan. Home loans benefit the buyer not only regarding gaining an asset but also in terms that it's a good instrument of saving and for employed ones it turns out to be the source of tax benefit also.

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